

Explanatory power by vagueness. Challenges to the strong prior hypothesis on hallucinations exemplified by the Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome

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ABSTRACT

Predictive processing models are often ascribed a certain generality in conceptually unifying the relationships between perception, action, and cognition or the potential to posit a ‘grand unified theory’ of the mind. The limitations of this unification can be seen when these models are applied to specific cognitive phenomena or phenomenal consciousness. Our article discusses these shortcomings for predictive processing models of hallucinations by the example of the Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome. This case study shows that the current predictive processing account omits essential characteristics of stimulus-independent perception in general, which has critical phenomenological implications. We argue that the most popular predictive processing model of hallucinatory conditions – the strong prior hypothesis – fails to fully account for the characteristics of nonveridical perceptual experiences associated with Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome. To fill this explanatory gap, we propose that the strong prior hypothesis needs to include reality monitoring to apply to more than just veridical percepts.

1. Introduction

Predictive processing (henceforth PP) is a set of closely related frameworks (see, e.g., [Piekariski, 2021](#) or [Wiese & Metzinger, 2017](#)) aiming to unravel the processes of the human mind and brain. It has become very popular in brain science over the last decades as it is considered a powerful and promising approach with strong explanatory power and versatility. To the same extent to which it is promising, big promises are made by proponents of the PP framework. Some accounts aim to explain attention mechanisms ([Hohwy, 2012](#)), others to understand action ([Friston et al., 2011](#)), and yet others not only try to provide a unifying theory describing the link between the brain and bio behavior ([Friston, 2009](#)) but go even further and aim to explain the dynamics and mechanisms underlying living systems in general ([Ramstead et al., 2018](#)). According to some ambitious intellectuals, PP even yields the potential to posit a ‘grand unified theory’ of the mind ([Clark, 2013](#)).

The impact of PP and its importance for neuroscience are apparent. Yet the extent of its explanatory power is not undisputed, as the obstacle such seemingly omnipotent theories often face is the tendency to oversimplify the respective matters at hand or to display a certain ignorance bias towards aspects of the investigated phenomena. The expected or even promised power of a seemingly all-

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explaining theoretical framework can drive it into the abyss of triviality or exuberant generality. As Sun and Firestone (2020) argue, this is what happened to behaviorism, and PP yields the potential to fall prey to the same pitfall (see, also, Sims, 2017). Other, no less essential issues concern epistemological aspects, consciousness, conscious perception, and phenomenology, among others (PiekarSKI, 2021; Wiese & Metzinger, 2017). The latter ones will be addressed in this present article. More precisely, what will be discussed in this paper are PP accounts of hallucinations. Within the PP framework, hallucinatory conditions are usually described as an imbalance between priors and sensory input that s to disturbances in sensory information processing and subsequent aberrant (interpretation of) percepts (see Collerton et al., 2023). Most commonly, said imbalance is claimed to be caused by an overweighting of priors (Cassidy et al., 2018; Corlett et al., 2019; O'Callaghan et al., 2017; Powers et al., 2017; Powers et al., 2016). In what follows, said PP approaches to hallucinations will be referred to as strong prior hypothesis.

As will be demonstrated, a strong tendency towards simplification or vagueness can be observed in the literature supporting the strong prior hypothesis. Furthermore, there seems to prevail an ignorance bias regarding phenomenological aspects of conscious perception in the hallucinatory mind. Challenging the strong prior hypothesis – on the one hand, by a general critique of how it deals with important concepts and definitions; on the other hand, by applying its analysis of hallucinations on visual pseudohallucinations – shows that while it might be applicable to explain the emergence of nonveridical percepts, the account lacks explanatory power regarding the conscious perception of such nonveridical images. We argue that in many instances, they fail to sufficiently differentiate between types of (aberrant) conscious visual perception.

Instead of reducing a vaguely defined concept of hallucinations to strong priors, we propose that it would be more fruitful to consider different types of hallucinatory conditions (i.e., perceptual experiences of nonveridical content) by incorporating a level of reality monitoring into the strong prior account. This level informs the model whether a given percept is attributed to the external world or identified as being internally generated by evaluating different dimensions of veridicality (see Seth, 2014) of the percept. Recent work has tried to bridge gaps between different approaches to visual hallucinations and to form a unified framework (Collerton et al., 2023).¹ Said work discusses and integrates, among others, PP explanations of hallucinations as well as reality monitoring accounts. However, we do not interpret this framework as a final solution to the problem of describing and understanding visual hallucinations. As the authors acknowledge, their framework “will allow theories to be more easily compared and integrated in the future” and “provides a structure for investigating potential common and individual causative pathways” (Collerton et al., 2023, p.11). Since their proposed synthesis builds on the strong prior hypothesis, we find that most aspects of our critique of the strong prior hypothesis also apply to Collerton et al.'s (2023) framework. Hence, we consider our discussion and arguments a valuable step towards a more fine-grained picture of differing hallucinatory conditions and a better understanding of the nuances that distinguish them.

2. Background

2.1. Predictive processing

As outlined above, PP is a prominent framework in various scientific disciplines concerning cognition and the brain. Naturally, differing interpretations or definitions of PP exist throughout the scientific community, which complicates providing a straightforward, widely acceptable description of the framework. In a substantial review, PiekarSKI (2021) filtered out common denominators of the various PP versions that exist, resulting in a list of five properties: 1) The brain entails a generative model that displays multilevel and hierarchical properties. It is generative in the sense that it generates predictions about the state of its environment; 2) The hierarchical structure of the cerebral cortex coincides with the model (i.e., the model can be mapped onto the anatomy of the brain); 3) The model aims to reduce prediction error (PE). PE can be understood as the difference between the prediction and the actual information it receives; 4) The model spans various levels of information processing; 5) Information processing happens bi-directionally. Top-down processing entails predictions about the information passed on from lower levels, while bottom-up processing conveys information about PEs. Information about the size of PEs is used for weighting the precision of predictions.

In general, PP frameworks ascribe the generative model Bayesian properties. As such, it is assumed that the model computes an *a posteriori* probability distribution (usually referred to as the *posterior*) by merging an already existing *a priori* distribution (the *prior*) with a *likelihood* of the appearance of specific information. The prior, hence, refers to the status quo of the state of the model. As such, the prior constitutes the top-down pathway of information processing. The likelihood puts the prior in relation to the incoming information (Wiese & Metzinger, 2017). This empirical application of Bayes' rule is thought to be an efficient method the brain employs to minimize PE (PiekarSKI, 2021). This process of checking the prior against incoming information happens at every level of the hierarchy. At any given level, predictions about the hypotheses at the respective subordinate levels are tested and updated using the PE. This results in a cascade of increasingly abstract information exchange that hierarchically runs between low-level sensory input to high-level cognitive mechanisms in a feedforward-feedback manner (Kwisthout et al., 2017; PiekarSKI, 2021).

Prior beliefs are essential in PP models of perception, but there are many ambiguities about their origin and interpretation. First, priors have to be understood as part of the model and should not be conflated with the more intuitive understanding of beliefs occurring in, for example, Belief-Desire-Intention models of psychology (Smith et al., 2022). In predictive processing models, priors are part of the predictive hierarchy that the brain uses to explain sensory input. They arise through updating beliefs about the state of the environment. A possible explanation of the origin of prior beliefs includes even more abstract hyperpriors, which represent general

¹ We want to thank the reviewers for bringing this recent work to our attention, which gave us the opportunity to include this contribution in our discussion.

Important concepts.

- **Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome:** A condition in which perceptual content is not caused by an external source. It can be caused by impairments of the visual pathway that lead to hyperactivity in the visual cortex.
- **Hallucination:** The perception of internally generated sensory experiences are misinterpreted as externally caused sensory inputs.
- **Pseudohallucination:** The perception of internally generated sensory experiences which may be perceived as (in terms of, e.g., their vividness or content) but not misinterpreted as externally caused sensory inputs.
- **Nonveridical perceptual experience:** The experience of percepts that are internally generated. This term does not make any assumption about the given percept's interpretation or quality of experience. Hence, it is a general term that refers to, i.a., hallucinations, pseudohallucinations, dreams, mind wandering, etc.
- **Predictive Processing:** A framework according to which the brain generates a model of the world and makes predictions about future states of said model. Predictions are compared to actual sensory input and a prediction error is calculated. The model is updated or actions are undertaken in order to minimize prediction error.
- **Prior:** In predictive processing, prior refers to the current state of the internal model given by prior probabilities about certain events. Priors are used to derive predictions about incoming signals and are compared to the actual state of the environment to calculate prediction error.
- **Strong Prior Hypothesis of Hallucinations:** Much predictive processing literature aims to explain hallucinations with strong priors. It is assumed that overly strong priors lead to a misinterpretation of spontaneous activity as actual sensory input.
- **Reality Monitoring:** The brain not only processes signals of external origin but also can generate internal signals (e.g., inner speech, mind wandering). Reality monitoring is the process that distinguishes internal from external signals.
- **Veridicality:** This term refers to whether a percept is perceived as real. The notion of veridicality is usually subdivided into three levels: subjective, objective, and doxastic veridicality (see chapter 2.2).

beliefs about the world's causal structure before making observations. In the influential 2013 paper "Whatever next? Predictive brains, situated agents, and the future of cognitive science", Clark argues that a further explanation of hyperpriors is not needed in a hierarchical model:

"Such appeals to powerful (and often quite abstract) hyperpriors will clearly form an essential part of any larger, broadly Bayesian, story about the shape of human experience. Despite this, no special story needs to be told about either the very presence or the mode of action of such hyperpriors. Instead, they arise quite naturally within bidirectional hierarchical models ... (Clark, 2013, p. 196)".

In this paper, we stick to the mathematical definition of priors as used in Bayesian approaches to cognition in general. All cognitive systems that perform Bayesian inference have some prior knowledge of the state of the environment before making observations, which is the prior $P(state)$. With the likelihood of an observation given the state of the environment $P(observation|state)$ and the probability $P(observation)$ the prior belief is updated according to Bayes rule:

$$P(state|observation) = P(state) * P(observation|state) / P(observation)$$

This updated belief $P(state|observation)$ is the posterior, which acts as a new prior for subsequent observations.

The Free Energy Principle (FEP) is a principle about self-organization of cognitive systems that can be used to ground PP accounts of brain function (Friston, 2019). In a nutshell, it says that all living systems minimize free energy, an upper bound on how surprising perceptual states are. Lowering the upper bound leads to a minimization of surprise that can either happen by updating the cognitive model of what caused the perception or by actively interfering with the environment states to make them fit the prediction. Taking the latter as a central feature of inference leads to active inference, a process theory incorporating the FEP into sense-making, which is compatible with the PP framework (Parr et al., 2022). Active inference has recently been used to integrate subjective experience into mathematical models of cognition (Sandved-Smith et al., 2021). Notable applications include time perception (Albarracin et al., 2022), attention and meta-awareness (Sandved-Smith et al., 2021), and folk-psychology (Smith et al., 2022). A possible extension of the strong-prior account that will be discussed in the course of this paper could build on this recent work on active inference to include subjective phenomenological qualities of nonveridical perceptual experiences. This formalization of subjective experiences is collected under the umbrella term computational phenomenology. Following our argument, an active inference model that explains phenomenological qualities of hallucination needs to include some form of reality monitoring.

2.2. Hallucinatory conditions and the Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome

Nonveridical percepts may come in numerous forms and originate from various causes (Bachmann, 2021). Therefore, providing exact and precise definitions of such perturbed percepts has proven challenging (Telles-Correia et al., 2015). Commonly, hallucinations are defined as perceptions without an actual cause in the external world. For example, in their work promoting the strong prior hypothesis, Corlett and colleagues use the following definition: "Hallucinations [...] are percepts without corresponding external

stimuli” (2019, p.114). Such a definition can be found frequently in a broad range of literature investigating hallucinations from different perspectives (e.g. in clinical contexts (Chiu, 1989; Waters et al., 2014), in neurobiological explanations (Boksa, 2009), in computational modeling (Reichert et al., 2013), etc.) or aiming to use hallucinations to present an argument or exemplify some aspects of a framework. As such, this way of specifying hallucinations is also found in the work promoting the strong prior hypothesis (e.g., Cassidy et al., 2018; Corlett et al., 2019; Powers et al., 2017; Powers et al., 2016).

Such a definition might suffice for distinguishing hallucinations from illusions (defined as internally generated erroneous percepts based on a false interpretation of physical content and hence being shared with other perceivers (Hamburger et al., 2017)). However, defining them in such a manner lacks precision and is therefore considered an oversimplification as it leaves unconsidered several vital aspects. It goes without saying that this yields limitations in providing a sound explanation of hallucinatory conditions. As discussed in the subsequent sections, such implications include, most prominently, the neglect of phenomenological aspects of different forms of experiencing nonveridical percepts and a limited capacity to distinguish such varying types of perceptual contents. This general problem inevitably also affects the strong prior hypothesis.

One such factor, particularly interesting for this present purpose, is whether affected individuals have insight into the unreal nature of what they perceive. This difference is of importance both from theoretical standpoints as well as from clinical ones. From a theoretical point of view, examining the exact properties of hallucinations, illusions, and whatever concepts might be found in their conceptual periphery² can be used to narrow down and refine the concept of consciousness (Hamburger et al., 2017). From a clinical perspective, a fine-grained understanding of perceptual perturbations is vital to characterize certain psychopathological conditions, inform models, and potentially refine treatment strategies (Collerton et al., 2023).

The Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome (henceforth CBS) is a condition mainly characterized by said difference between hallucinations with and without insights. It describes the experience of unreal images without psychiatric comorbidity due to impaired vision (Cammaroto et al., 2008; de Morsier, 1967; ffytche, 2005). Comparing case studies reveals that the percepts emerging in CBS show great variability in complexity and content while usually maintaining a high level of clarity, detail, and vividness. Buttar and Kaell (2018) present a case study of an 80-year-old woman who reported seeing organisms with tentacles. Höflich et al. (2012) describe the case of a 75-year-old man whose hallucinations manifested in manifold ways: plants growing out of tables, hedgehog-like animals walking around on the ground, chessboard patterns on the walls, skyscrapers rising from the ground in time-lapse, or mudslides crashing into the room he resided in. A case report by Stojanov (2016) describes the case of an 81-year-old woman who started to see white pigeons. Vacchiano et al. (2019) present the case of a 62-year-old man who reported seeing small cartoon-like images in blue and red, which later changed to colored mosaics or blue and white flashes. Finally, there are the explorations by Charles Bonnet (1760) himself, who reports visual hallucinations containing people, carriages, or buildings, as perceived by his 89-year-old grandfather. Teunisse et al. (1996) examined over 500 visually impaired patients and analyzed the cases of CBS. For 77 % of the subjects, the perceptions lack any personal meaning. The main categories the percepts consist of are people (80 %), animals (38 %), plants/trees (26 %), buildings, inanimate objects, or other scenes (15 %).

As mentioned above, a crucial aspect of CBS is that affected individuals have insight into the unreal nature of the experienced percepts. Therefore, this characteristic constitutes a crucial diagnostic criterion alongside features such as repetitiveness and persistence of simple or complex percepts, exclusive occurrence in the visual domain as well as the absence of other mental disorders or cognitive impairments (see Cammaroto et al., 2008; Höflich et al., 2012; Russell et al., 2018; Strong, 2019). Therefore, and in line with, e.g., Sedman (1966) or Hare (1973) (but see also Telles-Correia et al., 2015 or Turner, 2014), the term “pseudohallucination” is used in this report to refer to stimulus-independent perceptions with insight while “hallucination” will refer to stimulus-independent perceptions without insight.

The most prominent theory of the pathogenesis and -physiology of CBS holds that visual loss results in hyperactivity of (parts of) the visual cortex (Coltheart, 2018). This theory has found support by empirical work of different methodologies. Vacchiano et al. (2019) describe the case of an individual suffering from Leber Hereditary Optic Neuropathy and experiencing CBS-like unreal visual percepts. The individual also experiences acquired audio-visual synesthesia, which triggers said percepts through auditory stimuli. The authors used that synesthetic phenomenon to induce such visual hallucinatory percepts during fMRI and show that the auditory stimulation was followed by activation in the primary and secondary visual cortex and the insula, cuneus, and precuneus. Another study found hypermetabolism in the ventral visual pathway employing FDG-PET, suggesting that this region shows increased activity (Sasaki et al., 2021). In an EEG experiment, Piarulli et al. (2021) observed an increase in alpha power in occipital and midline posterior areas, an increase in delta and theta band activity in midline posterior regions, as well as a power reduction in frontal areas when comparing resting-state and hallucinatory condition in a CBS patient. Further, brain stimulation demonstrates that stimulation of visual cortex areas can result in the perception of unreal visual images, as shown by Andelman-Gur and colleagues (2020).

Reality monitoring is a critical concept in differentiating pseudohallucinations from hallucinations, i.e., correctly identifying a nonveridical perceptual experience as internally generated versus misinterpreting it as externally caused. It refers to discriminating between internally versus externally generated perceptual experiences (Garrison et al., 2020; Simons et al., 2017). As such, perceptual reality monitoring plays a crucial role in ascribing properties of veridicality to sensory perceptions (Dijkstra et al., 2022). Hence, it follows that disruptions of this process may lead to trouble distinguishing the real from the imagined, as would be the case in hallucinatory conditions (Garrison et al., 2020). In the literature, impaired reality monitoring is often associated with hypoactivity in medial parts of the anterior prefrontal cortex or connectivity problems with such frontal areas (Fazekas, 2021; Waters et al., 2021).

² See, e.g., Sanati (2012) Sanati (2012) or Waters et al. (2021), who propose that different stimulus-independent perceptions such as hallucinations, dreams, or imagery may not be distinct phenomena with clear borders but rather share commonalities.

Given that, the decrease of power in frontal activity, as observed by [Piarulli et al. \(2021\)](#), seems somewhat contradictory. If a reduction in frontal activity potentially leads to reality monitoring impairments, how do CBS patients maintain insight? The answer might be found in posteromedial cortical regions. [Piarulli and colleagues \(2021\)](#) observed an increase in power in these areas. Also, [Vacchiano et al. \(2019\)](#) reported higher activity in the precuneus during the experience of unveridical percepts in their patient. According to [Garrison et al. \(2020\)](#), the precuneus, a part found in said posteromedial region, seems to play an essential role in the correct functioning of reality monitoring.

Moreover, reality monitoring is theorized as more than just a mechanism responsible for monitoring the origin of percepts. Recent work tries to show that this mental machinery exhibits parallels with metacognition, ascribing it properties of a multilevel architecture that yields the potential to explain the phenomenological difference between the knowing versus the experiencing of whether a percept is real or not ([Dijkstra et al., 2022](#)). This is interesting in the present context since CBS is characterized by experiencing unveridical percepts as if they were real. That is, the nonveridical visual content that CBS patients experience can have the same vividness, detailedness, etc., as the veridical content. Still, patients commonly acquire and maintain an understanding of the unreal nature of the perceived nonveridical percepts and are capable of distinguishing them from percepts that actually correspond to events or objects in the external world.

Reality monitoring and maintaining insight constitute a crucial component of this contextualization. As discussed above, the cognitive capacity of reality monitoring is considered an essential component of both unimpaired and perturbed perception ([Dijkstra et al., 2022](#); [Fazekas, 2021](#)). [Seth \(2014\)](#) proposed a model that offers a handful of tools that might help narrow down what exactly said notion of insight might be. Initially, this so-called PPSMC model (Predictive Perception account of SensoriMotor Contingencies) asks how perceptual presence – the experiencing of perceptual contents as real, existing parts of the external world – is not given in synesthesia even though the percepts might very well seem as being generated by an external process. Despite this initial focus, the framework also lends itself to describing perceptual contents of other sorts. It does so by establishing perceptual reality and veridicality as model-specific working concepts. Veridicality, in turn, houses three dimensions: subjective, doxastic, and objective veridicality, which are defined by [Seth \(2014\)](#) as follows:

Perceptual reality: the existence of a vivid perceptual phenomenology.

Subjective veridicality: the phenomenological appearance of perceptual content as part of the external world.

Doxastic veridicality: the cognitive understanding that given perceptual contents reflect the external world or parts of it.

Objective veridicality: given when perceptual content does reflect, at least to some extent, features of the external world.

For example, in the case of normal, unimpaired perception, all the above-mentioned dimensions apply. At the same time, in non-lucid dreaming, objective veridicality is not given, as the perceptual contents do not reflect properties of the external world. The model also considers two kinds of hallucinations: with versus without delusions. The latter include, among others, also CBS. While delusional hallucinations, such as schizophrenic psychotic episodes, share the same veridicality dimensions with non-lucid dreaming, CBS and lucid dreaming exhibit the same properties. In both cases, the percepts appear perceptually real and subjectively veridical, while objective veridicality is not given. However, on a doxastic level, the individual maintains unimpaired reality-checking and thus knows that the perceived content is not part of the external world. Hence, applying the terminology of [Seth \(2014\)](#) to the above-elaborated working definitions of pseudohallucinations versus hallucinations shows that the dimension of doxastic veridicality is the crucial factor in distinguishing those two phenomena.

3. PP accounts for hallucinations and the strong prior hypothesis

In the framework of PP, perceptual and cognitive disturbances are generally explained as failures of sensory predictions. [Adams et al. \(2014\)](#) discuss hallucinatory conditions as a result of poor balancing between priors and incoming sensory data. More precisely, they suggest an overweighting of prior expectations as a causing factor. [Corlett and colleagues \(2019\)](#) review experiments that show that even in healthy subjects, hallucinations can be triggered by strong priors. One such experiment, applying a Pavlovian learning task, was conducted by [Powers et al. \(2017\)](#). The authors suggest strong perceptual priors to be the primary underlying mechanism. Also, in hallucinatory states of mind that are not induced in experimental settings, such as in schizophrenia ([Cassidy et al., 2018](#); [Kaminski et al., 2019](#)) or post-traumatic stress disorder ([Lyndon & Corlett, 2020](#)), an overweighting of priors is assumed to be among the causing factors.

There is, in fact, some empirical work supporting such assumptions. [Stuke et al. \(2021\)](#) investigated whether socially meaningful visual stimuli are perceived differently in individuals with differing levels of psychosis proneness. By applying a Bayesian decision model, the authors first assessed the participant's priors to different socially meaningful stimuli. They then looked for correlations between the degree of psychosis proneness and prior and found significant positive correlations between the two variables. [Cassidy and collaborators \(2018\)](#) tested the role of dopamine in the context of the strong-prior hypothesis in schizophrenic patients. Assuming that this neuromodulator is involved in a gain-control process, which, in turn, might manifest in an overweighting of priors, the authors pharmacologically manipulated dopamine levels in their participants. They found correlations between hallucinatory percepts and perceptual biases, which, as the investigators state, posits a reflection of disproportional gain on priors. An overweighting of priors was also found in Lewy body disease-related visual hallucinations ([Zarkali et al., 2019](#)). The authors presented two-tone images that were hard to disambiguate on their own but easy to disambiguate when prior information was given to two groups of patients of Lewy body disease – one that experienced visual hallucinations and one that did not – and healthy individuals. They measured discrimination sensitivity both before and after the cues were provided. The researchers found that hallucinators showed greater improvements in

discrimination sensitivity following the provision of information than non-hallucinators or controls. According to the authors, this suggests that experiencing visual hallucinations in Lewy body disease is correlated to an overweighting of priors.

Note that not all theories on the genesis of hallucinations are built upon top-down processes. For example, [Sterzer et al. \(2018\)](#) review approaches that argue for either top-down or bottom-up processes as potential causes of hallucinations. Also, [Corlett et al. \(2019\)](#) discuss data that challenges the strong prior approach. As such, they mention two phenomena: 1) the observation that corollary discharge³ seems to fail in schizophrenic conditions; 2) the immunity to certain visual illusions. Regarding challenge 1, the authors review that a large corpus of the literature suggests that said failure of corollary discharge in schizophrenia is a vital factor in the misattribution of inner speech to external sources, i.e., auditory hallucinations. According to [Corlett and colleagues \(2019\)](#), this seems to represent a case of weaker priors. As for problem 2, the authors present data from schizophrenia research that suggests that priors are too weak instead of too strong. To resolve those apparent contradictions, Corlett et al. suggest “[allowing] that these precise priors arise as a mollifying response to the uncertainty engendered by less precise prior elsewhere in the system” (2019, p.116). In the case of corollary discharge, this would be at parallel levels within the hierarchy of the network, while in the case of illusions, the less precise priors would occur at lower levels in the hierarchy. That “[h]ierarchy may be crucial here” ([Corlett et al., 2019](#), p.116) is an argument also shared by [Powers et al. \(2016\)](#). Both hallucinations and illusions originate from dynamic interactions between priors and prediction errors. It is not the interaction per se that determines whether and how perception might be disturbed, but rather the hierarchical level at which it occurs. If an unbalancing of priors and prediction errors happens at a lower level, it might lead to illusions. If the interactions are perturbed at a higher level, on the other hand, the outcome might be hallucinations.

However, some scholars disagree with the attempt to explain nonveridical perceptual experiences through PP. [Gallagher and colleagues \(2021\)](#) counter the PP approach by thoroughly reviewing and analyzing three different illusions: the *Müller-Lyer Illusion*, which works on a purely visual domain, as well as the *Rubber Hand Illusion* and the *Alien Hand Illusion*, which both apply to the visual domain but also include the misinterpretation of false body parts to be the own ones. The authors reject the assumption that perceptual experiences can or shall be explained by narrow and strict internalist accounts. That general principles of brain processes alone cause those illusions seems contradictory to the observation that cultural or environmental experience can alter how illusions are perceived or whether they are perceived at all. The authors argue that instead of trying to force culture- and environment-dependent embodied sensory-motor processes into a hierarchically structured brain architecture, the system as a whole should be seen as a system involving the brain, body, and environment. As such, the system proposed by [Gallagher et al. \(2021\)](#) would follow principles of metaplasticity. That is, brain and body, as well as environment and sociocultural practices, can influence each other and the system as a whole. Such a *4-or-more-E account*⁴ could include all factors influencing cognition, perception, and action. Still, this argument only rejects internalist and strictly representational interpretations of PP. Recent formulations of the free energy principle and active inference as underlying PP have interpreted the generative models as non-representational and cutting across brain, body, and environment in a sense compatible with the *4-or-more-E account* ([Ramstead et al., 2020](#)).

4. Challenges imposed by Charles-Bonnet-Syndrome

In their paper’s “Outstanding Questions” section, [Corlett et al. \(2019\)](#) ask whether their account of strong priors would *trans*-diagnostically apply to hallucinations. That is, they wonder whether their approach would also describe hallucinatory conditions outside of the realm of schizophreniform illnesses. As an example of such non-schizophrenia-related hallucinations, they name CBS, among others. The answer is quite likely no – at least not without adjusting and refining the strong-prior hypothesis – due to the fact that said approach leaves out several aspects that differentiate phenomena of perceiving nonveridical content.

One aggravating problem is the ignorance of the difference between the various nonveridical perceptual experiences by most of the theorizing work based on PP approaches. Most of the above-reviewed corpus of literature on PP accounts for hallucinatory conditions is overgeneralized and simplified. Corlett and colleagues use the following definition: “Hallucinations [...] are percepts without corresponding external stimuli” (2019, p.114). A very similar specification is given in the works by Powers et al. when they state: “Hallucinations (percepts without external stimulus) may arise when strong priors cause a percept in the absence of an input” ([Powers et al., 2017](#), p.1) or when they propose that “hallucinations – perceptions without stimulus – can be understood as top-down effects on perception, mediated by inappropriate perceptual priors” ([Powers et al., 2016](#), p.1). Also, Cassidy et al. are very much in line with this when they label “hearing voices in the absence of true speech stimuli” (2018, p.503) as auditory hallucinations.

A differentiation between distinct types of unveridical percepts might be negligible under certain circumstances. For example, if one were to focus exclusively on the emergence of such percepts. In the case of CBS, for instance, the above-discussed hyperactivity in visual areas could account for that. However, for CBS as a whole, this differentiation is crucial. If a theory does not explain why CBS patients realize the unreal nature of their perceptions and how they can distinguish real from unreal percepts – even though both might exhibit the same vividness – it does not explain CBS. What is instead provided is a generalized picture of some hallucinatory condition.⁵

³ Corollary discharge refers to an internally generated duplicate of a motor signal sent out to sensory areas whenever a certain motor command is initiated. This has two effects: 1) motor commands can be altered and adapted prior to their execution; 2) sensory areas are informed that the respective stimulation due to the motor action is self-generated and not the product of external forces ([Feinberg, 1978](#); [Garrison et al., 2017](#)).

⁴ embodied, embedded, extended, enactive, +ecological, +emotional ([Gallagher et al., 2021](#), p.16).

⁵ I allow myself at this point to share with the reader a little story that puts that in other words. At a guest lecture given by Prof. Semir Zeki in Vienna, he told us a little anecdote about a discussion he once had with a critic of one of his theories. The opponent set out his counterarguments to Prof. Zeki’s work. Listening closely to them, Prof. Zeki responded: “You’re absolutely right. But you’re only half-right. Therefore, you’re wrong.”.

As such, it is claimed that the strong prior hypothesis-based models of hallucinations under discussion tackle the emergence of percepts. However, the aspect of how those percepts are transduced to conscious perception and how real percepts can be distinguished from unreal ones is missing. That is, the differing phenomenological qualities of different forms of hallucinatory experiences are overlooked and not sufficiently dealt with. In itself, this would not be a problem if the scope of the strong prior hypothesis was clearly communicated. However, statements such as “[r]ecent data establish a role for strong prior beliefs in the genesis of hallucinations” (Corlett et al., 2019, p.114), while actually quite vague in their nature, lead to believe that the strong prior hypothesis covers hallucinations entirely. This issue is being discussed among scholars, and even strong promoters acknowledge that PP would benefit from “better articulation of [...] empirical predictions generated when subsuming a phenomenon under PP” (Hohwy, 2020, p.221).

Suppose a theory of hallucinatory states does not deal with the mechanisms that enable or disable conscious insights into the unreal nature of perturbed percepts but rather exclusively tackles the processes that potentially lead to the sensational manifestation of such perceptions. In that case, it is but a theory of precursors of conscious perception. This is also what Marvan & Havlík (2021) state in their critique of predictive processing accounts for conscious perception. Their work argues that modern-day predictive theories fail to account for conscious perception, let alone consciousness. They question whether predictive accounts can explain conscious perception beyond the mere identification of candidate prerequisites and question whether the transitions from unconscious to conscious perception necessarily depend on predictive mechanisms – a critique that is reflected in this present discussion of the strong prior hypothesis. Also, Wiese (2018), although acknowledging attempts at that problem (e.g., Friston, 2018; but also see Solms, 2019), argues that the mere minimizing of prediction error cannot account for consciousness as several conscious states would lack properties usually associated with consciousness. Finally, Seth and Hohwy (2020) claim that predictive approaches do not provide a theory for consciousness itself but rather for consciousness science.

The open question is not how the percepts in CBS emerge but rather how an individual that experiences such percepts manages to identify their nonveridicality, no matter how real and vivid they might seem. Or, to use the terminology introduced in the preceding sections: What process defines a percept’s veridicality on a doxastic level? An attempt at explaining could be made by drawing on hyperpriors, similar to how Clark (2013) discusses hyperpriors as underlying mechanisms of binocular rivalry. As such, a hyperprior is supposed to exist, posing that it cannot occur in the real world that both eyes perceive entirely different things. Similarly, one could argue that a hyperprior exists, posing that objects, whether persons, entities, animals, or the like, do not just occur out of nowhere.

Such a hyperprior-based escape, however, is troublesome on many levels. On the one hand, it would only reverse the problem by explaining how unreal percepts in pseudohallucination are correctly identified but would leave the question of why this identification fails in hallucinations unanswered. On the other hand, applying context-specific, superordinate rules is not innocuous, as it might lead to just arguing in terms of hyperpriors whenever an explanatory obstacle emerges (similar to the concerns by Sun & Firestone (2020) warning that self-prediction might lead PP to the same dilemma self-reinforcement led behaviorism into – a lack of explanatory power by trivially explaining everything). Further, experimental data shows that in binocular rivalry, mixed percepts might very well be perceived (Klink et al., 2017), thus weakening the hypothesis that hyperpriors explain binocular rivalry. Also, one might wonder: if such a hyperprior for binocular rivalry would exist, why doesn’t exist a similar one for the Alien Hand Illusion? Just like the fact that no two different percepts can occur in the two eyes separately, it should also be improbable that the own hand starts to do things contrary to the deliberate motor action. However, this illusion persists even when the subjects see the experimenter’s hand, as described by (Gallagher et al., 2021). Hence, an explanation purely based on potential hyperpriors can be discarded.

What is claimed here is that ignorance towards the vast range of unveridical perceptual experiences leads to an unjustified neglect of important aspects. Such a neglect bias inevitably leads to a set of false or imprecise assumptions to begin with. No sufficiently deep and accurate theorizing can arise from such a starting point. As pointed out above, definitions of essential concepts in the reviewed literature are hazy and cover much more than hallucinations alone. Stimulus-independent perception (i.e. perceiving contents that are not coupled to the external sensory environment) covers a vast range of phenomena, such as hallucinations, (day)dreams, fantasies, and imagery (Waters et al., 2021), synesthesia (Dijkstra et al., 2022; Seth, 2014), or mind-wandering (Fazekas, 2021). How, thus, should a framework accomplish to describe a phenomenon satisfyingly if its definition is so vague that it also fits numerous other phenomena? One could argue that all those phenomena are, in some way or another, the same: Dreams are hallucinations during sleep; synesthetic experiences are triggered cross-modal hallucinations; and fantasies, imagery, or mind-wandering are auto-created volitional hallucinations. On a superficial level, this line of argumentation might suffice. However, in order to achieve progress in understanding hallucinatory conditions – be it by means of PP or other frameworks – superficiality should be avoided where possible. As such, the present critique that current approaches to hallucinatory conditions based on the strong prior hypothesis lack explanatory power to account for the phenomenological difference between hallucinations and pseudohallucination prevails.

That pseudohallucinations are very seldomly considered in the PP literature even though a considerable amount of work exists on different stimulus-independent perceptive experiences is an observation that is in line with the criticism by Litwin & Miłkowski (2020), which states that PP models tend to re-describe already known phenomena. Another recent review noted that a common critique of PP models is that they often operate under ideal circumstances and conditions (Piekarski, 2021). Similarly, Gallagher and colleagues (2021) claim that certain principles in PP accounts are ‘in principle’ principles, as they call it. Approaches to hallucinatory conditions such as the ones by Powers et al. (2016) or Corlett et al. (2019), among others, build on unprecise definitions of hallucinations. Pseudohallucinations, hence, are a good exemplification of that critique, as they, in a sense, fall out of line within a generalizing framework based on oversimplified ‘in principle’ assumptions.

5. Discussion and future perspectives

The strong prior hypothesis aims to explain hallucinatory conditions as a result of an imbalance between priors and sensory input,

where priors are assumed to be overweighted. This approach is a valid contribution to a better understanding of the mechanisms that underlie hallucinations. However, it fails to capture a detailed picture due to leaving important aspects unattended. As such, it is argued here that the strong prior hypothesis is exactly that – a first approximation – rather than an explanation. In order to appropriately differentiate between miscellaneous types of unveridical perceptions, such as hallucinations, pseudohallucinations, dreams, mind-wandering, or the like, it is imperative to consider reality monitoring mechanisms and how they operate on different levels of veridicality.

Hence, we propose an extension to the strong-prior hypothesis as a first step toward accounting for the discussed differences. This extended model includes an additional layer of awareness that evaluates if nonveridical percepts are interpreted as internally vs. externally generated. Excessive gain on the prior expectation can explain the perception of an image that is not linked to environmental stimuli. A separate evaluation loop that judges its likelihood of being outside of one's imagination could account for pseudohallucinations that are perceived but interpreted as unveridical. Fig. 1 shows this additional part of the prediction hierarchy as a kind of reality check for the top layer. If the percept is interpreted as real, we can understand them as true hallucinations, and if not, we model them as pseudohallucinations.

Our extension of how the strong-prior hypothesis models the perception of nonveridical sensory information is a next step to more accurately account for the differences between hallucinations and pseudohallucinations (and potentially other phenomena of non-veridical perceptual experiences). Recent work by Collerton and colleagues (2023) provides a unified framework that entails the core aspects of various leading theories of visual hallucinations – including PP as well as reality monitoring approaches. We concede that Collerton et al.'s (2023) work touches on similar topics, and acknowledge their valuable contribution to this ongoing discussion. Yet, their framework could, nevertheless, benefit from our analysis. As it includes arguments inspired by the strong prior hypothesis, it is ultimately prone to similar problems. Some aspects of our argument on reality monitoring are accounted for by their framework, while others, such as insight and pseudohallucinations, are insufficiently discussed. Different models focus on different aspects, are built on different premises, or follow varying inherent logics. We therefore strongly encourage their attempt to bridge gaps between approaches and find their common denominators.

However, other aspects are less thoroughly dealt with. For instance, their discussion of reality monitoring is solely grounded in work tackling Parkinson's disease (i.e., Barnes et al., 2003) rather than general and more recent discussions of reality monitoring (e.g. Simons et al., 2017). Closely related, the phenomenon of pseudohallucinations and, concomitantly, the aspect of insight are hardly covered at all. Countering this critique, one might argue that Collerton et al.'s (2023) work touches on visual hallucinations exclusively and, hence, does not consider divergent phenomena. However, the authors do differentiate hallucinations from dreams or illusions. More importantly, they mention CBS. Hence, their model is built on a similar ignorance bias as the strong prior account. Lastly, their framework does not clearly indicate what the concept of veridicality really refers to. In the various instances of definitions of hallucinations (which, incidentally, also vary in their precision), the authors provide conceptualizations of veridicality that are not entirely clear. In Table 2, the authors contrast hallucinations with “veridical or illusionary perception of things which are in the visual environment” (Collerton et al., 2023, p.5.) This suggests objective veridicality. Congruent with that, the authors state elsewhere in the text the following: “Given that the primary distinction between a veridical and a hallucinatory subjective perception lies in its relationship to what is really out there” (2023, p.4). However, they then proceed as follows: “we have taken the default position that the subjective quality of both hallucinations and veridical perceptions are the same” (ibid). This latter statement suggests the level of subjective rather than objective veridicality.

This brief discussion of Collerton et al.'s (2023) work demonstrates that the concerns raised in the present critique of PP approaches to hallucinations that follow the strong prior hypothesis are valid after all. It is evident that other aspects, approaches, or concepts need to be discussed. In combination with our proposal, this shall serve as thought-provoking impulses for future research.

In recent work, Fazekas (2021) lays a potential foundation for a general framework to unify mind-wandering, dreaming, and hallucinations. The author starts his approach by observing that the relationship between these phenomena has been mostly neglected in the literature. However, as the author concludes, they seem closely related. It is argued that mind-wandering and hallucinations share most properties, i.e., they occur spontaneously, transiently, and relatively unconstrained. Further, Fazekas (2021) reviews literature that suggests that hallucinations might very well happen in individuals with intact reality monitoring. But there is also the opposite case that individuals with impaired reality monitoring do not turn out to be prone to experiencing hallucinations. Therefore, the author does not base his approach on impaired reality monitoring but on the imagery vividness of percepts, which can influence the functioning of the reality monitoring system. That is, it is claimed that mind-wandering and hallucinatory conditions (at least non-clinical ones) are based on the same processes – spontaneous increase in activity in sensory areas associated with the perceived content coupled with frontal hypoactivity⁶ as well as augmented default mode network activity – but that an overly intense posterior activation can trick the reality monitoring system into confusing the internally generated images with externally generated ones.

In their work on the role of attentional systems in hallucinatory states of mind, Shine and colleagues (2014) discuss the interplay between the visual network, the default mode network, as well as the ventral and dorsal attention networks. The authors specifically include pseudohallucinations in their analysis and contrast them with hallucinations. They, too, report increased default mode network activity across hallucinatory states. What seems to distinguish hallucinations from pseudohallucinations, according to their observations, is differences in ventral vs. dorsal attention networks.⁷ That is, pseudohallucinations appear to be characterized by a

⁶ More specifically, Fazekas (2021) mentions the medial aspect of the anterior prefrontal cortex as a key area.

⁷ Shine et al. (2014) ascribe the ventral attention network a major role in salience detection. The dorsal attention network, on the other hand, is involved in the attribution of exogenous attention.

Fig. 1. Extended Model of Hallucinations. **A)** A model of a perception process in the PP framework, where a prediction is sent to the model of perception, which in turn passes down an expected perception that is contrasted with sensory input to generate a prediction error. This prediction error goes up to the perceptual model and, in turn, changes predictions about environmental states. **B)** A proposed extension of the strong prior model of hallucinations is sketched. In the model, a strong prior is passed down to the model of perception, which increases the probability of perceiving what is expected and decreases the importance of actual sensory input. These hallucinations propagate back up the hierarchy, but in our extension, percepts are interpreted as veridical or not by reality monitoring parallel to the prediction. This extension allows for differentiation between hallucinations and pseudohallucinations.

decrease in activity in the ventral attention network as opposed to an increase in the dorsal attention network. Hallucinations, on the other hand, seem to display the exact opposite pattern.

Paraphrasing the above: existing evidence sheds light on diverging brain mechanisms underlying hallucinations, pseudohallucinations, as well as other phenomena of (impaired) sensory perception. The notion that, for example, hallucinations and illusions differ in the level of the hierarchy perturbations occur in (e.g., Corlett et al., 2019; Powers et al., 2016) is not wrong but incomplete. But what is its explanatory limit? The unprecise definition of hallucinations, as discussed above, adds even more to this vagueness. Keeping this in mind, let us briefly jump back to Fazekas: “As largely independent factors, misleading cognitive cues, misleading sensory cues and the dysfunction of the central reality monitoring system might underly different varieties of hallucinations to different degrees and in different combinations” (2021, p.7). What is significant about this statement in the context of this present paper is that the author emphasizes that various factors eventually make up a whole spectrum of phenomena of experiencing unveridical percepts. As was shown in the preceding sections, the discussed frameworks usually do not seem to bother much to take that into account. Given the popularity of such approaches and their objectives, acknowledging said bias is thus long overdue.

First and foremost, PP models of hallucinations – i.e., the strong prior hypothesis – need to undergo a refinement process, starting with establishing more precise working definitions as a basis for detailed analyses. Key concepts such as source attribution, reality monitoring, or veridicality must not be overlooked in order to be able to describe hallucinatory conditions sufficiently well. For example, as discussed above, hallucinations, dreams, and veridical perception share the same properties regarding source monitoring while differing on other levels, such as the state of consciousness or doxastic veridicality. Can strong priors alone account for that? Can strong priors alone account for the fact that both reality-belief and reality-experience are attributed to an external source in hallucinations, while in pseudohallucinations or lucid dreams, the belief dimension is shifted to an internal source? Recent work in the field of stimulus-independent perception highlights the role of source attribution, including its implications for the phenomenology of perception (Dijkstra et al., 2022) as well as the closely related concept of reality monitoring (Fazekas, 2021; Simons et al., 2017). Concerning the latter, the PPSMC framework proposed by Seth (2014) can be considered a seminal contribution and a utile toolbox as it provides both a model for perceptual reality and perceptual veridicality.

Also, recent work on phenomenal force - the quality of experience that perception reflects reality as it is - has explored the links of reality monitoring to PP (Gładziejewski, 2023). The author reformulates phenomenal force as a process of Bayesian inference, which is compatible with our proposal to extend the strong prior hypothesis with a more fine-grained PP model. Future attempts to explore PP processes underlying nonveridical perceptual contents need to be able to explain the different dimensions of veridicality and their relation to perceptual reality, as those concepts constitute fine-grained levels of analysis of perceptual contents and hence offer the tools for identifying and distinguishing certain perceptual conditions.

Remodeling the theoretical foundations of PP accounts must go hand in hand with empirical research. Thus, findings from neuroimaging and clinical studies and similar sources must find their way into theory construction; simultaneously, theoretical assumptions must be tested experimentally (see, e.g., the discussions by Collerton et al., 2023; Haarsma et al., 2022; O’Callaghan et al., 2017). Therefore, a PP theory of CBS should consider that the condition goes along not only with hyper-excitability in the visual cortex, even though the nonveridical percepts reflect the specialization of the respective hyperactive visual sub-region (ffytche et al., 1998). PP accounts of hallucinations must also consider the processes of reality monitoring. As such, prefrontal cortical areas play a crucial role (Allen et al., 2008; Simons et al., 2017) because hypo-activity in those regions or impaired connectivity between prefrontal and sensory areas could lead to perturbed reality monitoring (see Fazekas, 2021, or Waters et al., 2021)). However, altered activity in the

default mode network also influences whether the reality monitoring system works adequately (Fazekas, 2021). Lastly, the paracingulate cortex is also reported to be a critical region in reality monitoring processes (Garrison et al., 2020).

Hence, it should be investigated how exactly differences in activity in said regions, as well as connectivity between them, are manifested in the various kinds of unveridical perceptual experiences as well as in unimpaired perception. Subsequently, PP approaches must transduce and incorporate such findings in their framework. It does undoubtedly not satisfy rigorous scientific demands to simply claim that strong priors cause both hallucinations and illusions and that the difference is merely the hierarchical level said priors occur at. However, this is done in, e.g., Corlett et al. (2019) or Powers et al. (2016). This attempt at explanation not only suffers from the above-mentioned neglect bias but, to no lesser extent, from a vagueness regarding the hierarchical level in which the supposed strong priors appear. The same applies to experimental data on CBS. For example, in the study of Vacchiano et al. (2019), the authors seem to focus solely on sensory areas, thus neglecting the potential role of prefrontal regions and the paracingulate cortex in reality monitoring.

Further, due to the relatively low prevalence of CBS and the fact that it is somewhat complicated to investigate this condition, neuroimaging studies are scarce and often only case studies (e.g., Piarulli et al., 2021, or Vacchiano et al., 2019). A shortage of data naturally and inevitably puts limits on creating a detailed model. In general, both more as well as more precise empirical data are needed to construct and support satisfying theories or models of CBS and the whole spectrum of unveridical perceptions.

Another example of an aspect that would deserve more careful consideration in the models of hallucinations discussed in this paper is the neuromodulatory effects of neurotransmitters. For example, in a recent PP account of depression, Fabry (2020) outlines the roles of neurotransmitters in post-synaptic gain alterations of prediction error units. Neurochemistry is less profoundly investigated for CBS (but also for conditions characterized by stimulus-independent percepts in general). Still, some existing work may serve as inspiration for future research. Recalling the work of Cassidy et al. (2018) reviewed above, there seems to be a link between strong priors and striatal dopamine. Referring to the work by Yu and Dayan (2002) on the role of cholinergic modulation in perceptual inference, Reichert et al. (2013) discuss acetylcholine as a potential factor influencing the occurrence of unveridical percepts in CBS by balancing feedback and feedforward processing in the cortical hierarchy. It might be a fruitful approach to check for different neuromodulatory alterations and relate them to the prefrontal hypo- and sensory hyperactivity and the role of the paracingulate cortex and the default mode network discussed in the previous paragraphs.

6. Concluding remarks

The present article aims to show that acknowledging the difference between hallucinations and pseudohallucinations, as exemplified by CBS, challenges the explanatory power and scope of the strong prior hypothesis as proposed by PP accounts on hallucinatory states of mind. However, the critique is not restricted to CBS alone. Instead, CBS is meant to serve as an example of the details that current PP models of specific cognitive phenomena fail to explain. The underlying problem, a neglect bias and a subsequent imprecision in crucial properties might likely apply to other phenomena linked to stimulus-independent perceptive experiences and, therefore, to the broader picture of conscious perception. As such, our argument can be summarized as this: to fully explain hallucinations, the PP model needs to be extended to be able to account for all possible sub-phenomena and their respective features and characteristics. It is not claimed that PP frameworks lack the power to explain the recognition and identification of unreal percepts in CBS. However, whether they do or do not will have to be clarified by future theories, models, and experiments. The strong prior accounts of hallucinations are not inherently wrong, but they lack the depth to model different types of hallucinations. In their current state, they merely account for the emergence of percepts, but they fail to explain how unveridical experiences are perceived and interpreted. Adding an additional layer in the hierarchy that evaluates the strong prior would allow to differentiate between hallucinations, which are interpreted as veridical, and pseudohallucinations, which are perceived as external but interpreted as internally generated.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

F.R. Schmid: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Project administration. **M. Kriegleder:** Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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References

- Adams, R. A., Brown, H. R., & Friston, K. J. (2014). Bayesian inference, predictive coding and delusions. *AVANT. The Journal of the Philosophical-Interdisciplinary Vanguard*, *V*(3), 51–88. <https://doi.org/10.26913/50302014.0112.0004>
- Albarracín, M., Pitliya, R. J., Ramstead, M. J. D., & Yoshimi, J. (2022). Mapping Husserlian phenomenology onto active inference (arXiv:2208.09058). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.09058>.
- Allen, P., Laroi, F., McGuire, P. K., & Aleman, A. (2008). The hallucinating brain: A review of structural and functional neuroimaging studies of hallucinations. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *32*(1), 175–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2007.07.012>
- Andelman-Gur, M. M., Gazit, T., Strauss, I., Fried, I., & Fahoum, F. (2020). Stimulating the inferior fronto-occipital fasciculus elicits complex visual hallucinations. *Brain Stimulation*, *13*(6), 1577–1579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brs.2020.09.003>
- Bachmann, T. (2021). “Normal” hallucinations and attention. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, *15*, Article 731600. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2021.731600>
- Barnes, J., Boubert, L., Harris, J., Lee, A., & David, A. S. (2003). Reality monitoring and visual hallucinations in Parkinson’s disease. *Neuropsychologia*, *41*(5), 565–574. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0028-3932\(02\)00182-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0028-3932(02)00182-3)
- Boksa, P. (2009). On the neurobiology of hallucinations. *Journal of Psychiatry & Neuroscience: JPN*, *34*(4), 260–262.
- Bonnet, C. (1760). Essai analytique sur les facultés de l’ame. Les freres Cl. & Ant. Philibert. <http://archive.org/details/b30409135>.
- Buttar, B. S., & Kaelin, A. T. (2018). Hallucinations in an Elderly Patient with Severe Visual Impairment. *Cureus*, *10*(11), e3592.
- Cammaroto, S., D’Aleo, G., Smorto, C., & Bramanti, P. (2008). Charles Bonnet syndrome. *Functional Neurology*, *23*(3), 123–127.
- Cassidy, C. M., Balsam, P. D., Weinstein, J. J., Rosengard, R. J., Slifstein, M., Daw, N. D., Abi-Dargham, A., & Horga, G. (2018). A perceptual inference mechanism for hallucinations linked to striatal dopamine. *Current Biology*, *28*(4), 503–514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2017.12.059>
- Chiu, L. (1989). Review articles: Differential diagnosis and management of hallucinations. *Journal of the Hong Kong Medical Association*, *41*(3), 292–297.
- Clark, A. (2013). Whatever next? Predictive brains, situated agents, and the future of cognitive science. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, *36*(3), 181–204. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X12000477>
- Collerton, D., Barnes, J., Diederich, N. J., Dudley, R., ffytche, D., Friston, K., Goetz, C. G., Goldman, J. G., Jardri, R., Kulisevsky, J., Lewis, S. J. G., Nara, S., O’Callaghan, C., Onofrij, M., Pagonabarraga, J., Parr, T., Shine, J. M., Stebbins, G., Taylor, J.-P., ... Weil, R. S. (2023). Understanding visual hallucinations: A new synthesis. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *150*, 105208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2023.105208>.
- Coltheart, M. (2018). Charles bonnet syndrome: Cortical hyperexcitability and visual hallucination. *Current Biology*, *28*(21), R1253–R1254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.09.007>
- Corlett, P. R., Horga, G., Fletcher, P. C., Alderson-Day, B., Schmack, K., & Powers, A. R. (2019). Hallucinations and strong priors. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *23*(2), 114–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2018.12.001>
- de Morsier, G. (1967). The Charles Bonnet syndrome: Visual hallucinations in the aged without mental deficiency. *Annales Medico-Psychologiques*, *2*(5), 678–702.
- Dijkstra, N., Kok, P., & Fleming, S. M. (2022). Perceptual reality monitoring: Neural mechanisms dissociating imagination from reality. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *135*, Article 104557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2022.104557>
- Fabry, R. E. (2020). Into the dark room: A predictive processing account of major depressive disorder. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, *19*(4), 685–704. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11097-019-09635-4>
- Fazekas, P. (2021). Hallucinations as intensified forms of mind-wandering. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *376*(1817). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0700>
- Feinberg, I. (1978). Efference copy and corollary discharge: Implications for thinking and its disorders. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, *4*, 636–640. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/4.4.636>
- ffytche, D. H. (2005). Visual hallucinations and the charles bonnet syndrome. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, *7*(3), 168–179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-005-0050-3>
- ffytche, D. H., Howard, R. J., Brammer, M. J., David, A., Woodruff, P., & Williams, S. (1998). The anatomy of conscious vision: An fMRI study of visual hallucinations. *Nature Neuroscience*, *1*(8), 738–742. <https://doi.org/10.1038/3738>
- Friston, K. (2009). The free-energy principle: A rough guide to the brain? *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *13*(7), 293–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2009.04.005>
- Friston, K. (2018). Am I Self-Conscious? (Or Does Self-Organization Entail Self-Consciousness?). *Frontiers in Psychology*, *9*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00579>
- Friston, K. J. (2019). Waves of prediction. *PLOS Biology*, *17*(10), e3000426. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000426>
- Friston, K., Mattout, J., & Kilner, J. (2011). Action understanding and active inference. *Biological Cybernetics*, *104*(1–2), 137–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00422-011-0424-z>
- Gallagher, S., Hutto, D., & Hipólito, I. (2021). Predictive Processing and Some Disillusions about Illusions. *Review of Philosophy and Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13164-021-00588-9>
- Garrison, J. R., Bond, R., Gibbard, E., Johnson, M. K., & Simons, J. S. (2017). Monitoring what is real: The effects of modality and action on accuracy and type of reality monitoring error. *Cortex*, *87*, 108–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2016.06.018>
- Garrison, J. R., Saviola, F., Morgenroth, E., Barker, H., Lührs, M., Simons, J. S., Fernyhough, C., & Allen, P. (2020). Did I imagine that? The functional role of paracingulate cortex in reality monitoring (p. 2020.05.19.103572). bioRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.05.19.103572>
- Gładziejewski, P. (2023). The rational role of the perceptual sense of reality. *Mind & Language*, *38*(4), 1021–1040. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mila.12445>
- Haarsma, J., Kok, P., & Browning, M. (2022). The promise of layer-specific neuroimaging for testing predictive coding theories of psychosis. *Schizophrenia Research*, *245*, 68–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2020.10.009>
- Hamburger, K., Graben, K., & Neuf, H. (2017). Hallucination – Consciousness – Illusion. *Perception*, *46*(6), 645–649. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0301006616684906>
- Hare, E. H. (1973). A short note on pseudo-hallucinations. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, *122*(569), 469–476. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.122.4.469>
- Höfllich, A., Baldinger, P., Lanzemberger, R., & Kasper, S. (2012). Steckbrief seltener Krankheiten: Das Charles Bonnet Syndrom. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery and Psychiatry*, *13*(4), 187–189.
- Hohwy, J. (2012). Attention and conscious perception in the hypothesis testing brain. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *3*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00096>
- Hohwy, J. (2020). New directions in predictive processing. *Mind & Language*, *35*(2), 209–223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mila.12281>
- Kaminski, J. A., Sterzer, P., & Mishara, A. L. (2019). “Seeing Rain”: Integrating phenomenological and Bayesian predictive coding approaches to visual hallucinations and self-disturbances (Ichstörungen) in schizophrenia. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *73*, Article 102757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2019.05.005>
- Klink, P. C., Boucherie, D., Denys, D., Roelfsema, P. R., & Self, M. W. (2017). Interocularly merged face percepts eliminate binocular rivalry. *Scientific Reports*, *7*(1), 7585. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-08023-9>
- Kwisthout, J., Bekkering, H., & van Rooij, I. (2017). To be precise, the details don’t matter: On predictive processing, precision, and level of detail of predictions. *Brain and Cognition*, *112*, 84–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2016.02.008>
- Litwin, P., & Milkowski, M. (2020). Prospection does not imply predictive processing. *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, *43*, e137. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X19002991>

- Lyndon, S., & Corlett, P. R. (2020). Hallucinations in posttraumatic stress disorder: Insights from predictive coding. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology, 129*(6), 534–543. <https://doi.org/10.1037/abn0000531>
- Marvan, T., & Havlík, M. (2021). Is predictive processing a theory of perceptual consciousness? *New Ideas in Psychology, 61*, Article 100837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.newideapsych.2020.100837>
- O'Callaghan, C., Kveraga, K., Shine, J. M., Adams, R. B., & Bar, M. (2017). Predictions penetrate perception: Converging insights from brain, behaviour and disorder. *Consciousness and Cognition, 47*, 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2016.05.003>
- Parr, T., Pezzulo, G., & Friston, K. J. (2022). Active inference: The free energy principle in mind, brain, and behavior. *The MIT Press*. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12441.001.0001>
- Piarulli, A., Annen, J., Kupers, R., Laureys, S., & Martial, C. (2021). High-density EEG in a charles bonnet syndrome patient during and without visual hallucinations: A case-report study. *Cells, 10*(8), Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells10081991>
- Piekarski, M. (2021). Understanding predictive processing. *A Review. Avant, XII*, 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.26913/avant.2021.01.04>
- Powers, A. R., Mathys, C., & Corlett, P. R. (2017). Pavlovian conditioning-induced hallucinations result from overweighting of perceptual priors. *Science, 357*(6351), 596–600. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan3458>
- Powers, A. R., III, Kelley, M., & Corlett, P. R. (2016). Hallucinations as top-down effects on perception. *Biological Psychiatry. Cognitive Neuroscience and Neuroimaging, 1* (5), 393–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpsc.2016.04.003>
- Ramstead, M. J. D., Badcock, P. B., & Friston, K. J. (2018). Answering Schrödinger's question: A free-energy formulation. *Physics of Life Reviews, 24*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plrev.2017.09.001>
- Ramstead, M. J., Kirchoff, M. D., & Friston, K. J. (2020). A tale of two densities: Active inference is enactive inference. *Adaptive Behavior, 28*(4), 225–239. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059712319862774>
- Reichert, D. P., Serié, P., & Storkey, A. J. (2013). Charles bonnet syndrome: Evidence for a generative model in the cortex? *PLoS Computational Biology, 9*(7), e1003134.
- Russell, G., Harper, R., Allen, H., Baldwin, R., & Burns, A. (2018). Cognitive impairment and Charles Bonnet syndrome: A prospective study. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry, 33*(1), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gps.4665>
- Sanati, A. (2012). Pseudohallucinations: A critical review. *Dialogues in Philosophy, Mental and Neuro Sciences, 5*(2), 42–47.
- Sandved-Smith, L., Hesp, C., Mattout, J., Friston, K., Lutz, A., & Ramstead, M. J. D. (2021). Towards a computational phenomenology of mental action: Modelling meta-awareness and attentional control with deep parametric active inference. *Neuroscience of Consciousness, 2021*(1), niab018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nc/niab018>
- Sasaki, H., Fujimoto, Y., Ima, H., & Kageyama, Y. (2021). Visualization of hypermetabolism in the ventral visual pathway by FDG-PET in the Charles Bonnet syndrome. *Clinical Neurology and Neurosurgery, 208*, Article 106832. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clineuro.2021.106832>
- Sedman, G. (1966). A comparative study of pseudohallucinations, imagery and true hallucinations. *The British Journal of Psychiatry: The Journal of Mental Science, 112* (482), 9–17. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.112.482.9>
- Seth, A. K. (2014). A predictive processing theory of sensorimotor contingencies: Explaining the puzzle of perceptual presence and its absence in synesthesia. *Cognitive Neuroscience, 5*(2), 97–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17588928.2013.877880>
- Seth, A. K., & Hohwy, J. (2020). Predictive processing as an empirical theory for consciousness science. *Cognitive Neuroscience, 1–2*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17588928.2020.1838467>
- Shine, J. M., O'Callaghan, C., Halliday, G. M., & Lewis, S. J. G. (2014). Tricks of the mind: Visual hallucinations as disorders of attention. *Progress in Neurobiology, 116*, 58–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pneurobio.2014.01.004>
- Simons, J. S., Garrison, J. R., & Johnson, M. K. (2017). Brain mechanisms of reality monitoring. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 21*(6), 462–473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2017.03.012>
- Sims, A. (2017). The Problems with Prediction. In T. K. Metzinger, & W. Wanja (Eds.), *PPP - Philosophy and Predictive Processing*. Open MIND. Frankfurt am Main: MIND Group.
- Smith, R., Ramstead, M. J. D., & Kiefer, A. (2022). Active inference models do not contradict folk psychology. *Synthese, 200*(2), 81. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-022-03480-w>
- Solms, M. (2019). The Hard Problem of Consciousness and the Free Energy Principle. *Frontiers in Psychology, 9*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02714>
- Sterzer, P., Adams, R. A., Fletcher, P., Frith, C., Lawrie, S. M., Muckli, L., Petrovic, P., Uhlhaas, P., Voss, M., & Corlett, P. R. (2018). The predictive coding account of psychosis. *Biological Psychiatry, 84*(9), 634–643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2018.05.015>
- Stojanov, O. (2016). Charles Bonnet syndrome. *Vojnosanitetski Pregled, 73*(9), 881–884. <https://doi.org/10.2298/VSP1503211140S>
- Strong, J. (2019). "Playthings of the Brain": phantom visions in charles bonnet syndrome. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work, 62*(5), 586–596. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01634372.2019.1631927>
- Stuke, H., Kress, E., Weinhhammer, V. A., Sterzer, P., & Schmack, K. (2021). Overly strong priors for socially meaningful visual signals are linked to psychosis proneness in healthy individuals. *Frontiers in Psychology, 12*, 1083. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.583637>
- Sun, Z., & Firestone, C. (2020). The dark room problem. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences, 24*(5), 346–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2020.02.006>
- Telles-Correia, D., Moreira, A. L., & Gonçalves, J. S. (2015). Hallucinations and related concepts—Their conceptual background. *Frontiers in Psychology, 6*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00991>
- Teunisse, R. J., Cruysberg, J. R., Hoefnagels, W. H., Verbeek, A. L., & Zitman, F. G. (1996). Visual hallucinations in psychologically normal people: Charles Bonnet's syndrome. *Lancet (London, England), 347*(9004), 794–797. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(96\)90869-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(96)90869-7)
- Turner, M. A. (2014). A short note on pseudohallucinations. *Psychopathology, 47*(4), 270–273. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000358065>
- Vacchiano, V., Tonon, C., Mitolo, M., Evangelisti, S., Carbonelli, M., Liguori, R., Lodi, R., Carelli, V., & La Morgia, C. (2019). Functional MRI study in a case of Charles Bonnet syndrome related to LHON. *BMC Neurology, 19*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-019-1579-9>
- Waters, F., Barnby, J. M., & Blom, J. D. (2021). Hallucination, imagery, dreaming: Reassembling stimulus-independent perceptions based on Edmund Parish's classic misperception framework. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences, 376*(1817), 20190701. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0701>
- Waters, F., Collerton, D., Ffytche, D. H., Jardri, R., Pins, D., Dudley, R., Blom, J. D., Mosimann, U. P., Eperjesi, F., Ford, S., & Larøi, F. (2014). Visual hallucinations in the psychosis spectrum and comparative information from neurodegenerative disorders and eye disease. *Schizophrenia Bulletin, 40*(Suppl_4), S233–S245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/sbu036>
- Wiese, W. (2018). Toward a mature science of consciousness. *Frontiers in Psychology, 9*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00693>
- Wiese, W., & Metzinger, T. K. (2017). Vanilla PP for Philosophers: A Primer on Predictive Processing. *PPP*. <https://doi.org/10.15502/9783958573024>
- Yu, A. J., & Dayan, P. (2002). Acetylcholine in cortical inference. *Neural Networks: The Official Journal of the International Neural Network Society, 15*(4–6), 719–730. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0893-6080\(02\)00058-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0893-6080(02)00058-8)
- Zarkali, A., Adams, R. A., Psarras, S., Leyland, L.-A., Rees, G., & Weil, R. S. (2019). Increased weighting on prior knowledge in Lewy body-associated visual hallucinations. *Brain. Communications, 1*(1), fcz007. <https://doi.org/10.1093/braincomms/fcz007>